

Annexes: Research instruments

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Annex 1: First questionnaire for teachers

Date: _____

Interviewee name: _____

Dear teacher:

The purpose of this instrument is to collect information on various aspects seeking to support a final graduation project about the differences that exist in the didactic analysis carried out by two teachers. The information collected will be confidential and will be used solely for academic purposes. We appreciate your collaboration.

1. Are you interested in participating in this research and each of the stages it contains?

Yes No

2. What is the highest academic degree you have in teaching mathematics?

<input type="checkbox"/> Professorship or Certification	<input type="checkbox"/> Master's degree
<input type="checkbox"/> Bachelor's degree	<input type="checkbox"/> Doctorate
<input type="checkbox"/> Licentiate's degree	<input type="checkbox"/> Postdoc

3. How many years have you worked as a teacher? (If you have worked less than 2 years, you should only complete up to this question)

2 years or less
 More than 2 years, but less than 5 years
 5 years or more

4. Have you had at least one institutional evaluation, with a rating of excellent in the last 5 years?

Yes No

5. How many times in the last five years have you taught mathematical content related to the subject matter of this study?

Never 1 time 2 times 3 times 4 times 5 times or more

6. How many times in the last two years of teaching have you participated in professional training activities in your discipline?

- Never 1 time 2 times 3 times 4 times 5 times or
more

Annex 2: Expert teacher information sheet

Name: _____

Characteristics of the expert teacher	Yes	No	Comments
a. Interest of the teacher to participate in the research			
b. Bachelor's or Licentiate's degree in Mathematics Teaching			
c. Practicing teacher, with five or more years of professional experience in classrooms			
d. Has institutional evaluations with a rating of excellent in the last five years			
e. Has taught the school mathematical content, about the topic of interest, more than once, in the last five years of teaching			
f. Participates in professional training activities in his discipline			

Annex 3: Novice teacher information sheet

Name: _____

Characteristics of the novice teacher	Yes	No	Comments
a. Interest of the teacher in participating in the research			
b. Bachelor's or Licentiate's degree in Mathematics Teaching			
c. Practicing teacher with at most two years of professional experience			

Annex 4: Second questionnaire for teachers

Universidad Nacional
Faculty of Exact and Natural Sciences – School of Mathematics

Final graduation work to obtain a Licentiate's Degree in Mathematics Teaching

Dear teacher

The purpose of this questionnaire is to guide teachers to carry out a didactic analysis of each of the short videos. The information collected will be confidential and will be used solely for academic purposes. We appreciate your collaboration.

Instructions. Based on the observation of the recorded class episode, please complete in detail the information requested.

General information
Date: _____ Questionnaire No.: _____
Aspects observed
1. Have quality mathematics been taught? Justify your answer. 2. Do you consider that the students have learned with the proposed tasks? Why? 3. Do you consider that the temporary resources, materials, ICTs, etc. used are adequate? Why? 4. Do the tasks and their management promote students' engagement? How? 5. Is the interaction in the class adequate and does it allow to solve students' difficulties? Explain. 6. Are the contents consistent with the curriculum and are they useful for students' social and labor insertion? Why?

Source: Font (cited by Araya, 2019).

Annex 5: Semi-structured interview

Universidad Nacional

Faculty of Exact and Natural Sciences – School of Mathematics

Final graduation work to obtain

a Licentiate's Degree in Mathematics Teaching

Dear teacher

The purpose of this interview is to complement the didactic analysis carried out by each of the teachers on the video sequences shown. The information collected will be confidential and will be used solely for academic purposes. We appreciate your collaboration.

General information
Name or code of the interviewee: Interviewer Name: Interview date: Interview location: Start time: Ending time:
Aspects observed
1. Of the aspect(s) observed in the video, which of them do you believe strengthen the teaching and learning processes carried out? 2. Why do you consider that the aspects selected in the previous question are more relevant with respect to the others? 3. Which aspect(s) observed in the video do you consider weaken the teaching and learning processes carried out? 4. With what actions can you improve the aspects highlighted in the previous question? 5. What aspects do you highlight about the development of mathematical content by the teacher? 6. What aspects stand out about the teacher's mediation strategies and why? 7. What aspects do you highlight about interactions between the teacher and the students

and why?

8. What aspects stand out about the relationship between the subject matter and the curriculum and why?

9. What aspects stand out about physical resources and student distribution and why?

10. What do you think was the most interesting thing you saw in the video sequences?

11. What aspects do you want to add to the analysis carried out?

Source: Prepared by the authors.

Annex 6: Subcategories and indicators

Epistemic suitability (ES)

Subcategory	Indicators
ESa. Situations- problems	ESa1. An appropriate contextualization of the subject and exercises is achieved through the presentation of daily life situations to students.
	ESa2. Situations in which problems are generated are proposed.
ESb. Languages	ESb1. Use of different forms of mathematical expression (verbal, graphic, symbolic...) by the teacher or the students.
	ESb2. Language level is appropriate for the students for whom the class is intended.
	ESb3. Situations of mathematical expression and interpretation are proposed.
ESc Rules	ESc 1. The definitions and procedures are clear and correct, and adapted to the educational level (of the students) for whom the class is intended.
	ESc 2. The fundamental statements and procedures of the subject matter are presented appropriately for the educational level.
	ESc 3. Situations are proposed where students have to generate their own definitions about propositions or procedures.
ESd. arguments	ESd1. The explanations, proofs and demonstrations are appropriate for the educational level (of the students) for whom the class is intended.
	ESd2. Situations are promoted in which students have to present arguments.
ESe. Relations	ESe1. The mathematical objects seen in class (problems, definitions, propositions, etc.) are related and connected to each other.
	ESe2. The various meanings of the objects that are involved in the practices are identified and articulated.

Source: Godino (2013)

Annex 7: Interactional suitability (IS)

Subcategory	Indicators
ISa. Teacher- student interaction	ISa1. The teacher adequately presents the topic (clear and well-organized, does not speak too quickly, emphasizes the key concepts of the topic, etc.).
	ISa2. Recognizes and resolves students' conflicts (questions and answers given are appropriate, etc.).
	ISa3. Consensus is sought based on the best argument.

ISa4. Various rhetorical and argumentative devices are used to get students engaged and capture their attention.

ISa5. Students' participation in the dynamics of the class is facilitated.

	ISb1. Dialogue and communication among students is promoted.
ISb. Interaction among students	ISb2. Students try to convince themselves and others of the validity of their statements, assumptions and answers, relying on mathematical arguments. ISb3. Group inclusion is promoted and exclusion is avoided.
ISc. Autonomy	ISc1. Times when students assume responsibility for the study are considered (they ask questions and present solutions; explore examples and counterexamples to investigate and make assumptions; use a variety of tools to reason, make connections, solve problems, and communicate).
ISd. Formative evaluation	ISd1. The teacher asks questions, proposes exercises to verify the learning obtained by students, among other things.

Source: Godino (2013)

Annex 8: Mediational suitability (MS)

Subcategory	Indicators
MSa. Material resources	MSa1. Resources and materials are used for carrying out activities. MSa2. The use of resources and materials is appropriate and contextualized for students. MSa3. Definitions and properties are contextualized and supported using situations, concrete models and visualizations.
MSb. Number of students, schedule and classroom conditions	MSb1. The number and distribution of students allows the planned teaching to be accomplished. MSb2. Classroom conditions are suitable for carrying out planned processes.
MSc. Time	MSc1. Sufficient time is devoted to the most important contents of the topic. MSc2. Sufficient time is devoted to the contents that are more difficult to understand.

Source: Godino (2013)

Annex 9: Ecological suitability (EcS)

Subcategory	Indicators
EcSa. Adaptation to the curriculum	EcSa1. The contents, their implementation and evaluation are adapted to the curricular guidelines.
EcSb. Opening towards educational innovation	EcSb1. Innovation based on research and reflective practice. EcSb2. Integration of new technologies (calculators, computers, ICTs, etc.).

EcSc. Socio-professional and cultural adaptation	EcSc1. Contents contribute to the socio-professional training of students.
EcSd. Education about values	EcSd1. Education about democratic values and critical thinking is incorporated.
EcSe. Intra and interdisciplinary connections	EcSe1. The contents are related to other intra- and interdisciplinary contents.

Source: Godino (2013)

Annex 10: Affective suitability (AS)

Component	Indicators
ASa. Interests and needs	ASa1. The proposed activities stimulate interest in the students. ASa2. The situations proposed in the activities promote awareness about the usefulness of mathematics in everyday life.
ASb. Attitudes	ASb1. The teacher promotes participation in activities, perseverance, responsibility, tolerance, etc., during the lesson. ASb2. Argumentation is carried out in conditions of equality; the argument is valued on its own terms and not by the person that presents it.
ASc. Emotions	ASc1. Self-esteem is promoted, avoiding rejection or fear of mathematics.

Source: Godino (2013)

Annex 11: Cognitive suitability (CS)

Component	Indicators
CSa. Prior knowledge	CSa1. Students have the previous knowledge necessary to study the topic (either they have studied it previously or the teacher plans for its study). CSa2. The various components of the planned content can be successfully taught (have a manageable level of difficulty).
CSb. Curricular adaptations to individual differences	CSb1. Activities are carried out that take individual differences into account. CSb2. Activities are carried out that reinforce the development of the students.
CSc. Learning	CSc1. Conceptual and propositional understanding; communicative and argumentative competence; situational understanding; metacognitive competence. CSc2. The evaluation takes into account different levels of problem solving.

Source: Godino (2013)

